

A Cross Sectional Study of Microbiological Pattern of Tracheal Aspirate in Tracheostomized Patients in a Tertiary Care Centre

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Abstract

Background: Over the past few decades, hospital acquired infections have grown more complicated. The danger of nosocomial infections is increased by the frequent use of invasive procedures in critical care units (ICUs), such as tracheostomy. With a rise in the prevalence of bacteria resistant to antibiotics, treatment of these infections with more broad-spectrum antimicrobials has created serious issues.

Aim: To study various microbiological pattern of tracheal aspirate in tracheostomized patients of tertiary care hospital.

Materials and Methods: The study is a tertiary care hospital based, cross sectional observational study, which was conducted with 150 tracheostomized patients to assess the various microbiological pattern of tracheal aspirate on day 1 of tracheostomy and day 7 post tracheostomy in these patients.

Results: 150 tracheostomized patients of age 12 to 70 years were included in the study. Clinic-epidemiological factors of the patients and microbiological pattern of tracheal aspirate were assessed. Factors such as intubation status pre tracheostomy, duration of hospital stay and antibiotics given were statistically significant for the tracheal aspirate microbial growth pattern on day 1 of tracheostomy and day 7 of tracheostomy.

Conclusion: The current study shows that patients receiving tracheostomy therapy have a significant chance of developing lower respiratory tract infections, which are typically brought on by gram-negative bacteria such *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, and *Acinetobacter* spp.

Keywords: Tracheostomy, tracheal aspirate, lower respiratory tract infections, culture and sensitivity.

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Introduction

One of the earliest known surgical procedures is a tracheostomy. Long-term respiratory failure is the most typical reason for tracheostomy in adults. Poor airway reflexes and a lowered degree of consciousness are two more signs. Additionally, tracheostomies can be performed to get around an obstruction and make tracheobronchial suction easier. Bacterial colonisation can happen after tracheostomy; specifically, bacteria can settle in the tracheobronchial tree of patients who have tracheostomies or endotracheal tubes, which raises the risk of respiratory problems, particularly those requiring ventilator support. Between 80% and 100% of adult tracheostomy patients experience colonisation, which is the presence of microorganisms without a corresponding host reaction; in contrast, colonisation occurs in 100% of paediatric patients [1]. Tracheobronchial colonisation is linked to more clinical diseases and may make one more susceptible to symptomatic infection. Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) is a common infection among paediatric patients undergoing open reconstructive operations (up to 32.5%). [2]

The most frequent PPM to colonise and infect the lower airways of adult tracheotomy patients are aerobic gram-negative bacilli, mainly *Pseudomonas* and *Serratia* species. In individuals with long-term tracheostomies, enteric gram-negative bacilli (EGNB) colonisation of the lower respiratory tract has been observed frequently.

To identify and treat lower respiratory tract infections, the doctors use tracheal aspirate specimens (LRTI). According to a 2012 study by Cline *et al.*, 54% of pulmonologists and 15% of otolaryngologists routinely acquired surveillance tracheal aspirate cultures from kids with tracheostomy tubes. 90% of pulmonologists and 80% of otolaryngologists who got surveillance cultures used these cultures to direct

treatment of acute chest infections when they materialized. [3]

Aim

To Study the Various microbiological pattern of tracheal aspirate seen in tracheostomized Patients of Tertiary Care Hospital.

Materials and Methods

In order to evaluate the varied microbiological patterns of tracheal aspirate in tracheostomized patients from September 2020 to October 2022, a cross-sectional observational study centred in a tertiary care centre used 150 tracheostomized patients admitted to the ward and critical care units.. Before the study could begin, permission from the institutional ethical committee was obtained. All the patients receiving tracheostomy in the 12- to 70-year-old age category of both sexes will be included except for those excluded due to exclusion criteria (those under 12 years of age, those over 70 years of age, and pregnant women).

Demographic data, admission date, placement in the ward or ICU, endotracheal intubation status prior to tracheostomy, date of tracheostomy, date of sample collection, and antibiotic medication prior to sample collection were all obtained from the eligible patients. The tracheal aspirate was obtained on days 1 and 7 following tracheostomy under strict aseptic conditions, and it was then transferred right away to the microbiology lab for sensitivity testing and culture. Data from the microbiology laboratory was gathered, and the most frequent bacteria identified in the culture sensitivity report of the tracheostomy swab was observed. Using the proper statistical techniques and procedures, the acquired data was analyzed. Both a numerical value and a percentage (%) were used to represent the category variables. The quantitative data, however, were shown as means with standard deviations and as a median with 25th and

75th percentiles (interquartile range). Using the Chi-Square test, the correlation between the qualitative variables was examined. P values less than 0.05 were regarded as statistically significant for purposes of analysis.

Results

Clinico-epidemiological factors of the patients and microbiological pattern of tracheal aspirate were assessed and results

are as follows. Mean value of age(years) of study subjects was 49.41 ± 16.14 with median (25th-75th percentile) of 52(38-64) (figure 1). 112(74.67%) patients were males and 38(25.33%) patients were females (figure 2). Majority [87(58.00%)] of patients were admitted in ICU. 63 out of 150 patients (42.00%) were admitted in ward (figure 3). Majority [109(72.67%)] of patients were intubated. Only 41 out of 150 patients (27.33%) were not intubated (figure 4).

In 108(72.00%) patients, indication was elective. Indication was emergency in only 42 out of 150 patients (28.00%) figure 5. In 122(81.33%)] patients, duration of hospital stay {Pre tracheostomy} was ≤ 7 days. Duration of hospital stay {Pre tracheostomy} was > 7 days in only 28 out of 150

patients (18.67%). Mean value of duration of hospital stay (days) {Pre tracheostomy} of study subjects was 5.09 ± 3.18 with median (25th-75th percentile) of 6(4.25-7) Figure 6.

In 10 (37.04%) patients, organisms detected in 1st sample collection was *Klebsiella pneumoniae* followed by *Escherichia coli* [6(22.22%)], mixed growth [6(22.22%)] and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* [4(14.81%)]. Organisms detected in 1st sample collection was *Enterobacter* species in only 1 out of 27 patients (3.70%) figure7.

In 38(24.36%) patients, organisms detected in 2nd sample collection was *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* followed by *Acinetobacter* species [35(22.44%)], *Klebsiella pneumoniae* [29(18.59%)], *Escherichia coli* [20(12.82%)] and mixed growth [20(12.82%)]. Organisms detected in 2nd sample collection was *Enterobacter* species in 14 out of 156 patients (8.97%) figure 8

Distribution of organisms detected in 1st sample collection was comparable with age(years) {12-30 years vs 31-45 years vs 46-60 years vs >60 years}. (Enterobacter species: - 0% vs 0% vs 0% vs 1.85% respectively (p value=1), Escherichia coli: - 3.70% vs 4% vs 0% vs 7.41% respectively (p value=0.291), Klebsiella pneumoniae: - 11.11% vs 8% vs 2.27% vs 7.41% respectively (p value=0.457), Pseudomonas aeruginosa: - 0% vs 4% vs 2.27% vs 3.70% respectively (p value=0.837), Mixed growth: - 3.70% vs 0% vs 6.82% vs 3.70% respectively (p value=0.761) (figure 8)

Distribution of organisms detected in 2nd sample collection was comparable with age(years) {12-30 years vs 31-45 years vs 46-60 years vs >60 years}. (Acinetobacter species:- 33.33% vs 32% vs 22.73% vs 14.81% respectively (p value=0.19), Enterobacter species:- 7.41% vs 8% vs 9.09% vs 11.11% respectively (p value=0.979), Escherichia coli:- 7.41% vs 12% vs 18.18% vs 12.96% respectively (p value=0.658), Klebsiella pneumoniae:- 11.11% vs 12% vs 22.73% vs 24.07%

respectively (p value=0.406), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*:- 29.63% vs 28% vs 15.91% vs 29.63% respectively (p value=0.399), Mixed growth:- 11.11% vs 12% vs 15.91% vs 12.96% respectively (p value=0.96)).(figure 9)

Distribution of organisms detected in 1st sample collection was comparable between male and female. (*Enterobacter* species: - 0.89% vs 0% respectively (p value=1), *Escherichia coli*: - 3.57% vs 5.26% respectively (p value=0.643), *Klebsiella pneumoniae*: - 8.04% vs 2.63% respectively (p value=0.453), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*: - 3.57% vs 0% respectively (p value=0.573), Mixed growth: - 2.68% vs 7.89% respectively (p value=0.171)). (Figure 10)

Distribution of organisms detected in 2nd sample collection was comparable between male and female. (*Acinetobacter* species: - 21.43% vs 28.95% respectively (p value=0.344),

Enterobacter species: - 9.82% vs 7.89% respectively (p value=1), *Escherichia coli*: - 12.50% vs 15.79% respectively (p value=0.606), *Klebsiella pneumoniae*: - 16.96% vs 26.32% respectively (p value=0.207), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*: - 25.89% vs 23.68% respectively (p value=0.787), Mixed growth: - 15.18% vs 7.89% respectively (p value=0.407)). (Figure 11)

Discussion

In our study, mean age (years) of research participants was 49.41 ± 16.14 with median of 52. Study done by Nagmoti *et al* [4] demonstrated stated the average age of the 30 participants in the research was 38.27. The youngest was three years old, while the oldest was 66. In our study, 74.67% patients were males and 25.33% patients were females, showing male predominance. Study done by Nagmoti *et al* [4] demonstrated that there were 19 (63%) males and 11 (37%) females, showing male predominance. Study done by Alrabiah A *et al* [5] demonstrated that the mean age of the participants was 57.5 years (SD: 16.48), with 33 (57%) of them being male. In our study 72.67% patients were intubated. 27.33% patients were not intubated.

Verma *et al*'s study [6] in Chicago revealed that anaerobic microbes play a significant role in pleuropulmonary infections. Usually, the pathogens that are implicated are endogenous. The recovery of the etiological agent from clinical specimens is the basis for the laboratory diagnosis of anaerobic pleural infections. The careful collection and transportation of uncontaminated samples is essential for the recovery of the causal agents, which was done in our current work. In our

study, in 84.67% patients, no growth from culture in 1st sample collection was seen. Growth in 1st sample collection was present in 15.33% patients. According to a study by Nagmoti *et al*. [4], of the 30 patients, 26 (87%) of them showed bacterial growth in aspirate on day 1 after tracheostomy, and 28 (93%) of them did so on day 8 after tracheostomy. *P. aeruginosa*, *Enterobacteriaceae* species, *A. baumannii*, and *S. aureus* were the most prevalent pathogens found in 82.4% of the patients, according to research by Alrabiah A. *et al*. [5].

P. aeruginosa was discovered in 47.7% of positive samples, which was within the 22%-54% range previously described in investigations, as either the only organism colonising the tracheostomy tube or in addition to other species done by Niederman M *et al* [7] and Bartlett JG *et al* [8].

In our study, in 37.04% patients, organisms detected in 1st sample collection was *Klebsiella pneumoniae* followed by *Escherichia coli* in 22.22%, mixed growth in 22.22% and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in 14.81%. Organisms detected in 1st sample collection was *Enterobacter* species in only 1 out of 27 patients (3.70%). In a research by Koirala *et al*. [9] from 2010 that had 45 patients, 90 percent of them developed bacterial growth after tracheostomies. In a 2011 research by Siddiqui *et al.*, 41 patients (82%) demonstrated growth in tracheal aspirate after tracheostomy.

In a research by Morar *et al*. [10] (1998), 95% of post-tracheostomy sites were colonised. In a 1996 study by Harlid *et al*. [11] in Sweden, they found that 83% of all sampling occasions revealed that patients had one or more possible pathogens colonised in their trachea. In our study, in 90.67% patients, growth from culture in 2nd sample collection was present. Growth from culture in 2nd sample collection was absent in 9.33%

patients. In our study, 24.36% of patients, organisms detected in 2nd sample collection was *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* followed by *Acinetobacter* species seen in 22.44%, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* seen in 18.59%, *Escherichia coli* seen in 12.82% and mixed growth seen in 12.82% patients. Organisms detected in 2nd sample collection was *Enterobacter* species in only 8.97% patients.

According to a study by Nagmoti *et al.* [4], *P. aeruginosa*, followed by *K. pneumoniae* and *Citrobacter* species, is the most typical organism found in tracheal aspirate specimens on days 1 and 8 after tracheostomy. On day 8, the *S. aureus* that was discovered in the specimens on day 1 was still present. MRSA and *Enterococcus* species were only isolated on day 8. On day 1 of the aspirate, there were 21 aerobic gram-negative bacteria (AGNB), which grew to 25 (86%) on day 8. From day 1 to day 8 post-tracheostomy, the number of isolates of aerobic gram positive cocci (GPC), which comprises *S. aureus*, Coagulase negative *Staphylococcus*, MRSA, and *Enterococcus* species, decreased from six (21%) to four (14%). From day 1 to day 8, *P. aeruginosa* persisted in six (20%) of the patients. In one (3%) of the patients, *K. pneumoniae* and *Enterococcus* species persisted.

P. aeruginosa and enteric gram-negative bacteria (*Escherichia coli*, *K. pneumoniae*, *Klebsiella oxytoca*, and *Enterobacter cloacae*) were the most prevalent in a study by Koirala *et al.* [9] in 2010, followed by *S. aureus*, other gram-negative bacteria, and *Viridans streptococci*. Of the 67 total isolates, 27 (or 40%) were *P. aeruginosa*. *K. pneumoniae* made up 11% of the sample, whereas the other enteric gram-negative bacteria made up 24% of it. As a result, there were 54 aerobic gram-negative bacteria in total (81%) which is consistent with the current study. On day 1, *S. aureus* was found in seven isolates (10%) as opposed to three (11%) in the current investigation, however

this was not the case on day 8 due to the lengthening of the tracheostomy. *P. aeruginosa* and *K. pneumoniae* were the predominate organisms in a research by Siddiqui *et al.* [12] in 2011, which is consistent with the current findings. Three (6%) patients had MRSA isolated, as opposed to one (4%) patient in the current investigation.

Aerobic gram-negative bacilli (AGNB), of which *P. aeruginosa* is the most prevalent pathogen, are responsible for more than 60% of nosocomial chest infections, according to a national nosocomial infections research carried out in the United States by Horan TC *et al* [13]. Since macrophages are known to generate elastase in response to these underlying chronic illnesses, this could be one explanation for the predominance of aerobic gram-negative bacterial colonisation (AGNB) in lower airways. According to research by Woods DE *et al* [14], the elastase is then secreted in saliva and depletes the mucosa of fibronectin, opening up receptor sites for aerobic gram-negative bacilli.

S. aureus and *S. pneumoniae*, which are common bacteria, can also adhere to the fibronectin. *P. aeruginosa* and *A. baumannii* were the most prevalent microorganisms populating the tube in a time frame less than 30 days following tracheostomy, according to a study done by Kumar KD *et al* [15]. This is in line with what we found, which showed that the two most prevalent organisms in the first quarter were *P. aeruginosa* and *A. baumannii*. Notably, the final two quarters' culture results did not produce *A. baumannii*.

Conclusion

In our study mean age (years) of research participants was 49.41 ± 16.14 with median of 52 with male predominance. 72.67% of patients were intubated. Mean value of duration of hospital stay (days) {Pre tracheostomy} of study subjects was 5.09 ± 3.18 days.

In 84.67% of patients no growth from culture in 1st sample collection was seen. In 90.67% of patient's growth from culture in 2nd sample collection was present. In 37.04% of patient's organisms detected in 1st sample collection was *Klebsiella pneumoniae* followed by *Escherichia coli* in 22.22%, mixed growth in 22.22% and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in 14.81%. In our study 24.36% of patient's organisms detected in 2nd sample collection was *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* followed by *Acinetobacter* species seen in 22.44%, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* seen in 18.59%, *Escherichia coli* seen in 12.82% and mixed growth seen in 12.82% patients. Organisms detected in 2nd sample collection was *Enterobacter* species in only 8.97% patients.

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